

ASSESSMENT OF OFF-GRID RENEWABLE ENERGY IN SELECTED AFRICAN COUNTRIES

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ABSTRACT

Access to reliable energy is a critical challenge in many African countries, particularly in rural areas. Despite abundant renewable resources, Africa's off-grid renewable energy capacity is low compared to global standards, highlighting the need for better resource assessment and utilisation. This study evaluates off-grid renewable energy capacities in selected African countries to assess their potential for sustainable energy in underserved regions without conventional grid access. In 2022, Africa's total off-grid renewable capacity was 1,422.51 MW, only 10.26% of the global capacity of 12,435.68 MW. While countries like the Congo DR and Kenya have relatively high capacities, overall deployment remains limited, indicating untapped potential to meet growing energy demands. The study recommends prioritising investments in off-grid renewable infrastructure, supported by strong policy frameworks and technological innovation, to enhance energy access, reduce fossil fuel reliance, and promote sustainable development. A commitment to renewable off-grid solutions is essential for providing clean, reliable energy and fostering economic growth across African nations, especially in isolated regions.

Keywords: Africa, Energy Access, Off-grid Renewable Energy, Sustainable Development, Untapped Potential.

INTRODUCTION

Energy access remains a fundamental driver of economic growth and social development. However, a significant proportion of Africa's population, particularly in rural areas, lacks access to reliable electricity. The International Energy Agency reports that approximately 600 million people in sub-Saharan Africa lack access to electricity, with national grids failing to extend to remote and underserved communities (Ebhotu & Tabakov, 2024; Ehimen et al., 2023). Off-grid renewable energy offers a viable solution to bridging this gap by utilizing decentralized energy sources such as solar, wind, hydro, and biomass. This paper examines the current capacity, deployment trends, and potential of off-grid renewable energy in selected African countries (Olajide et al., 2024; Salman et al., 2022). Energy access plays a crucial role in improving living standards, enhancing productivity, and fostering economic development (Iqbal & Noor, 2023; Kuponiyi et al., 2023; Li et al., 2024). Studies have shown that countries with higher electrification rates experience accelerated industrialization and improved socio-economic outcomes (Acheampong et al., 2021). In Africa, however, the electrification rate remains below 50% in many rural communities, limiting progress in key sectors such as education, healthcare, and small-scale enterprises (Adelokun & Olanipekun, 2020; Zebra et al., 2021).

Despite Africa's vast renewable energy potential, the continent has not fully harnessed its resources. For instance, Africa receives some of the highest levels of solar irradiation globally, yet solar energy contributes only a small fraction to total energy consumption (Abdelrazik et al., 2022; Adelokun & Olanipekun, 2019; IEA, 2022). Similarly, hydropower resources remain underutilized, despite the presence of major rivers such as the Congo, Nile, and Zambezi, which could support large-scale hydropower development (Carlino et al., 2023; IRENA, 2020; Omolola,

& Adedokun, 2020). Off-grid renewable energy systems refer to electricity generation and distribution solutions that operate independently of the national grid. These systems include mini-grids, stand-alone solar home systems, and decentralized wind or hydro installations. The adoption of off-grid solutions has gained momentum in recent years due to declining costs of solar photovoltaic (PV) panels, advancements in battery storage, and increased financing options (IRENA, 2023). One of the key benefits of off-grid renewable energy is its ability to provide electricity in remote areas where grid expansion is either technically challenging or economically unfeasible (Boute, 2016). Research indicates that decentralized solar PV mini-grids can deliver electricity to rural populations at a lower cost than extending national grids (Zeyringer et al., 2015). Furthermore, off-grid systems enhance energy security by reducing reliance on fossil fuels and improving climate resilience (Dahlan, 2022). From 2016 to 2020, off-grid renewable energy capacity in Africa experienced steady growth. The African Development Bank reports that investment in mini-grid and solar home systems increased significantly during this period, driven by international donor support and national electrification programs (AfDB, 2023). Countries such as Kenya, Nigeria, and Mali have made notable progress in scaling up off-grid solutions, with Kenya leading in the deployment of solar home systems (Adedokun et al., 2024; GOGLA, 2022; Medinilla & Sergejeff, 2023, Omolola & Adedokun, 2020). However, Africa's off-grid capacity remains relatively low compared to other regions. The total off-grid renewable energy capacity of selected African countries reached 1,416.68 MW in 2020, representing only a small fraction of global deployment (Adedokun et al., 2024). The slow pace of growth can be attributed to various challenges, including inadequate policy frameworks, limited financing options, and technical barriers (Babayomi et al., 2023).

Several factors hinder the widespread adoption of off-grid renewable energy in Africa:

- **Financial Constraints:** Access to capital remains a significant challenge for off-grid energy projects. Many rural communities have low purchasing power, making it difficult for private investors to recover costs.
- **Policy and Regulatory Barriers:** Inconsistent policies and lack of clear regulations for mini-grid development have slowed deployment in some countries.
- **Infrastructure Challenges:** Limited access to technical expertise, supply chain inefficiencies, and poor road networks make it difficult to deploy and maintain off-grid energy systems.
- **Awareness and Capacity Gaps:** Many rural communities lack awareness about off-grid renewable solutions and their benefits, resulting in slow adoption.

Despite these challenges, several opportunities exist for expanding off-grid renewable energy in Africa:

- **International Financing and Public-Private Partnerships:** Development finance institutions, such as the World Bank and AfDB, have increased funding for off-grid projects, creating opportunities for private sector involvement.
- **Technological Innovations:** Advances in battery storage, smart meters, and pay-as-you-go (PAYG) business models are making off-grid systems more affordable and efficient.
- **Community-Based Energy Initiatives:** Decentralized, community-driven energy projects have proven successful in countries such as Ethiopia and Tanzania, where cooperative ownership models have increased local acceptance and sustainability.
- **Policy Reforms and Electrification Strategies:** Governments are increasingly integrating off-grid energy into national electrification plans, providing policy support for expansion.

Energy access is a fundamental driver of economic development, yet millions of people in Africa, particularly in rural and remote areas, lack reliable electricity. Off-grid renewable energy offers a viable solution to bridge this energy gap. The increasing demand for sustainable energy sources, coupled with advancements in renewable technologies, has made off-grid solutions more feasible. This study assesses off-grid renewable energy capacity in selected African countries to understand their potential for enhancing energy access and supporting sustainable development.

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a quantitative research design to assess off-grid renewable energy adoption in selected African countries. A descriptive and comparative approach is used to analyze installed capacities, regional distribution, and trends. The study is based on secondary data analysis, utilizing published sources, including international energy reports, renewable energy databases, and governmental agencies. The data used in this study consists of global and African off-grid renewable energy installed capacities for 2022, as well as a breakdown of the top 15 African countries with the highest installed capacities. These datasets provide insights into Africa's share of the global off-grid renewable energy landscape and variations across different countries. To facilitate analysis, the data is processed using descriptive statistics to determine the central tendencies and dispersions of off-grid renewable energy installations. Additionally, graphical representations, including pie charts and bar charts, are utilized to visualize the distribution and disparities in installed capacities. A comparative analysis is conducted to evaluate differences among African countries and assess Africa's contribution to global off-grid renewable energy.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents and discusses the results obtained from the analysis of off-grid renewable energy capacity in selected African countries. The findings are based on the data from global and African off-grid renewable energy installed capacities and the ranking of the top 15 African countries by installed capacity. The results are interpreted using descriptive statistics, graphical representations, and comparative analysis to highlight key trends, variations, and the significance of off-grid renewable energy adoption in Africa.

Table 1: Global and African Off-Grid Renewable Energy Installed Capacity (MW) in 2022

Country	Offgrid Renewable Energy Installed Capacity (MW) 2022
World	12,435.68
Africa	1,422.51

Source: IRENA, 2023

Table 1 presents the total off-grid renewable energy installed capacity worldwide and in Africa as of 2022. The global off-grid renewable energy capacity stands at 12,435.68 MW, with Africa accounting for 1,422.51 MW of the global total. This highlights the relatively small share of Africa in the global off-grid energy sector, despite the continent's high potential for renewable energy sources such as solar, wind, and hydro. The data suggests a need for increased investments and policies to expand off-grid solutions in Africa to bridge the energy access gap.

Fig. 1: Chart of Global and African Off-Grid Energy Capacity (2022)

Fig. 1 illustrates the proportion of off-grid renewable energy installed capacity in Africa compared to the global total using a pie chart. Africa accounts for only 10.26%, while the rest of the world contributes 89.74% of the total off-grid renewable energy capacity. This stark difference emphasizes the limited adoption of off-grid renewable energy solutions across the continent. The visualization highlights the urgent need for Africa to scale up its investments in decentralized energy systems to address electricity access challenges, particularly in remote and rural areas where grid connections are not feasible.

Table 2. Off-grid Renewable Energy Capacity in Top 15 African Countries 2022

S/N	Country	Installed Capacity (MW) 2022
1	Algeria	123.20
2	Angola	48.66
3	Burkina Faso	29.65
4	Congo DR	164.49
5	Egypt	71.00
6	Ghana	16.03
7	Kenya	131.77
8	Malawi	83.92
9	Mali	79.01
10	Mozambique	30.71
11	Nigeria	37.64
12	Somalia	50.59
13	Sudan	135.57
14	Tanzania	56.85
15	Uganda	39.84

Source: Adelakun et al., 2024

Table 2 ranks the top 15 African countries based on their installed off-grid renewable energy capacity in 2022. Congo DR (164.49 MW), Sudan (135.57 MW), and Kenya (131.77 MW) emerge as the top three countries with the highest off-grid renewable energy capacity. In contrast, countries like Ghana (16.03 MW) and Burkina Faso (29.65 MW) have significantly lower installed capacities. The variation in off-grid renewable energy capacity among African countries indicates disparities in investment, policy frameworks, and natural resource utilization. Notably, countries with higher capacities often have robust government initiatives or external funding to support renewable energy projects.

Fig. 2: Chart Representation of Off-Grid Renewable Energy Capacity in the Top 15 African Countries in 2022

Fig. 2 provides a bar chart representation of the installed off-grid renewable energy capacity in the top 15 African countries. The visualization emphasizes the significant differences in renewable energy adoption across the continent. Countries such as Congo DR and Sudan have made substantial progress, whereas nations like Nigeria (37.64 MW) and Ghana have relatively lower capacities despite their large energy demands. This disparity suggests that while some countries have prioritized off-grid renewable energy, others still face policy, financial, and infrastructural barriers that hinder widespread adoption.

The study reveals significant disparities in off-grid renewable energy adoption across Africa and its contribution to the global energy landscape. Africa’s total off-grid renewable energy capacity of 1,422.51 MW accounts for only 10.26% of the global total of 12,435.68 MW. This indicates a

relatively low adoption rate despite the continent's vast renewable energy potential. The limited contribution suggests that many African countries still face challenges such as inadequate financing, weak policy frameworks, and insufficient technical infrastructure for expanding off-grid solutions. Among African nations, there are considerable differences in installed capacity. Countries like Congo DR (164.49 MW), Sudan (135.57 MW), and Kenya (131.77 MW) lead in off-grid renewable energy adoption, whereas nations such as Ghana (16.03 MW) and Burkina Faso (29.65 MW) have significantly lower capacities. This variation can be attributed to differences in national policies, access to funding, and government commitment to renewable energy. Countries with high capacities often have strong policy support, external investments, and favorable regulatory environments. The findings emphasize the urgent need for African nations to scale up off-grid renewable energy investments. By adopting supportive policies, leveraging international funding, and prioritizing decentralized energy solutions, African countries can bridge the electricity access gap and enhance sustainable development.

CONCLUSION

The assessment of off-grid renewable energy in selected African countries highlights the continent's relatively low contribution to global off-grid energy capacity and the significant disparities in adoption among nations. With a total off-grid renewable energy capacity of 1,422.51 MW, Africa accounts for only 11.44% of the global total of 12,435.68 MW, indicating a need for greater investments in decentralized energy solutions. Despite Africa's abundant renewable energy resources, such as solar, wind, and hydro, many countries still struggle with financing, policy limitations, and infrastructure challenges that hinder the widespread adoption of off-grid energy systems. The variation in installed capacity across African nations is evident, with Congo DR (164.49 MW), Sudan (135.57 MW), and Kenya (131.77 MW) leading in off-grid renewable energy deployment, while Ghana (16.03 MW) and Burkina Faso (29.65 MW) lag behind. These differences highlight the importance of strong policy frameworks, government support, and external funding in driving renewable energy adoption. Countries with robust energy policies and international partnerships tend to have higher off-grid energy capacities, emphasizing the role of governance and investment in accelerating growth. To enhance energy access and promote sustainability, African governments must prioritize off-grid renewable energy development through policy incentives, increased funding, and infrastructure expansion. Strengthening regulatory frameworks, fostering private sector participation, and leveraging international collaborations will be essential in scaling up off-grid renewable energy solutions across the continent.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Governments and private sectors should allocate more funds to develop and expand off-grid renewable energy projects in underserved areas.
- They should implement supportive policies, incentives, and regulations to encourage investment in off-grid renewable energy solutions.
- They should also promote research, development, and deployment of innovative renewable energy technologies suited for off-grid applications.
- Governments, businesses, and international organizations should foster collaborations to accelerate renewable energy deployment.
- They should invest in energy storage solutions such as batteries to ensure a stable and

reliable off-grid power supply.

- Communities should be educated on the benefits of renewable energy and be involved in planning and implementation.
- Governments and stakeholders should seek financial and technical assistance from global institutions and climate funds to scale up off-grid renewable energy projects.

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